

DEVELOPMENT OF A COMPOSITE AXLE HOUSING: A CASE STUDY IN MULTIDISCIPLINARY TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER MECHANISMS

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SUMMARY: This paper outlines a Teaching Company Scheme (TCS) project between Albion Automotive Driveline Division and the University of Strathclyde. The TCS acts as a technology transfer mechanism between universities and industry. The aim of the project is to produce an automotive structural component through the innovative use of fibre reinforced plastics (FRP). This project plays an important part in the company drive towards technological innovation. The attractiveness of composite materials to the automotive industry has been the opportunity for parts consolidation, weight savings and increased freedom of design. In meeting the project aim the requirements for the development of medium to high volume automotive composite componentry are met by the use of an integrated design and manufacturing methodology. This is coupled with an appreciation of the financial and marketing aspects required for the development of the components involved. The use of such an integrated and concurrent approach to the development and manufacture of an FRP component is an illustration of technology transfer in product design.

KEYWORDS: technology transfer mechanism, fibre reinforced plastics, feasibility study automotive structural components, integrated design and manufacturing methodology

INTRODUCTION

The transfer of technology provided by the TCS project is the introduction of an innovative design procedure encompassing several factors. These factors include the methodology of product, design, manufacture, marketing and financing. In the automotive industry which is generally concerned with mass production of components, the opportunity has arisen for the manufacture of components from composite materials. Such components are car body parts, springs and drive-shafts for commercial and other vehicles. There are new composite materials being developed which are giving potential for cost savings. New production procedures are making mass production more viable. The TCS is designed to provide companies with expertise to solve a problem that would otherwise lie dormant. The solution provided aims to be of strategic importance to the future development of the company. The university provides supervision and background expertise and makes this available to the Teaching Company Associate.

THE TCS SCHEME

The Centre for Advanced Structural Materials is a multidisciplinary unit within the University of Strathclyde, at the forefront of delivering innovative research and technology transfer solutions. The Centre is especially recognised for its work with Small to Medium Sized Enterprises (SMEs) which have been identified as crucial for the long term economic growth of the UK. One particularly successful technology transfer mechanism which the Centre employs is a UK government funding initiative called the Teaching Company Scheme (TCS).

The TCS is a collaborative programme where experts from higher education establishments participate in projects which are demonstrated to be central to specific industrial companies' plans for strategic development. The project work is carried out in the companies by young graduates known as Teaching Company Associates (TCAs) under the joint supervision of academic and industrial staff. The companies involved benefit from the research deliverables, the technology transfer process and by the training of a young graduate who not only develops technical skills but is also trained in the wider commercial implications of the research and development process. The academic institutions benefit from industrially significant case study material and develop their research capabilities in an innovative field of technology. The TCS is a vehicle for stimulating, developing and implementing innovative ideas.

ALBION AUTO INDUSTRIES

Albion Automotive as it is known today is an independent company formed on 26 November 1993 in a management buy out when the company DAF went into receivership. However it has been in existence since 1899 when the company was formed under the original name of Albion Motor Car Co Ltd in Glasgow. The company originally produced complete commercial vehicles in the form of light vans and also cars. In 1912 it took the decision to concentrate on the manufacture and development of commercial vehicles. Albion Automotive presently concentrates its business on the following areas of commercial vehicle manufacture; axle design and production, chassis component design and manufacture and crankshaft manufacture. The current product range caters for vans up to four tonnes and light/medium 4 x 2 and 4 x 4 wheel drive commercial and military trucks [1].

DESIGN METHODOLOGY USED FOR TCS PROJECT

The designer faces a different challenge when considering working with composites especially when the proposed component is to replace something which has been designed and constructed with traditional materials in mind (such as metals). Basically there are a whole set of new design considerations to be taken into account. The manufacturing process associated with it has also to be considered in detail as there may not be an existing process suitable. The creative element of product design in FRP materials covering shape, geometry, colour and surface texture is but one issue; the underlying emphasis being the technical aspects of the choice of materials, their properties, failure criteria, fabrication and processing methods.

There has to be an optimum integration of the above factors. Traditional materials (such as metals) have many design codes and material properties' data that allow for the accurate prediction of component performance. The costs of traditional materials are generally low

and therefore there may not be such a pressing need for optimisation. Perhaps the most important factor of all is that they are isotropic and essentially homogeneous.

From the first there has to be an understanding of the technical aspects of a new material. Such factors as reduced weight, freedom from corrosion, easier mouldability and fabrication need to be considered. This enables the technical benefits and drawbacks of the implementation of the new material to be thoroughly understood [2]. As soon as an assessment of the potential technical and performance benefits has been gained, it is then necessary to commence an assessment of the financial implications. This can be achieved by constructing a list of potential income and savings benefits against potential costs. The design methodology used in the project is based on the design methodology developed by Smith [3]. The component specification is based on one of Albion Automotive's current product range. However in the interests of aiming to avoid merely reproducing a copy of an existing part, the only restrictions placed upon the design of the component are at the interfaces between connected componentry in the design envelope.

Albion currently employ the use of advanced computer aided design (CAD) combined with finite element analysis (FEA) techniques in the design of their products. It is the concurrent development of a suitable manufacturing process and product design which is new to the company. Previously the company's policy has been to buy in rough castings of their products which are then machined to customers design specifications. The TCS project aims to deliver an appropriate design together with the manufacturing process to the company for the FRP component. This will enable the company to produce the product entirely in house which will alleviate the company's dependency on rough component suppliers. These have been competitors of Albion in the past and therefore the transfer of manufacturing technology in parallel with component design is seen as an important aspect of the project. The manufacturing method under consideration is the Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process.

DESIGN IMPLICATIONS FOR ALBION AUTO INDUSTRIES

Feasibility Study of the Rear Axle Casing

The component chosen for development at the start of the project was a rear axle casing (see fig.1). A feasibility study on the axle component was carried out. This was in order to assess the viability of the component's development in FRP where the financial and technical benefits were evaluated. The initial specification was based on the rear axle casing which Albion produce for the LDV 200 series van. The loads exerted upon the rear axle casing were determined in order to initialise suitable material selection.

The axle casing would have to be moulded in halves to allow the component to be manufactured by a satisfactory moulding process. The spindle ends would have to remain fabricated from metal due to customer / supplier demands for product compatibility. Attachments for suspension and brakes would have to remain metallic to avoid the potential redevelopment of the brakes / suspension. This problem could be addressed by incorporating metal inserts into the mould. However this would inevitably increase manufacturing costs with the incorporation of extensive adhesive bonding technology and additional forging / casting of metal inserts.

The rear axle casing would need to incorporate a driving gear system and metal spindle ends for stub axle attachment. The spring seats/suspension brackets were to be flexible in the design approach. It was thought that some form of cooling device would be necessary in the design to dissipate the heat generated by the driving head. The composite axle casing was to be based on the current old design incorporating a banjo casing as illustrated below in Fig 1.

The current rear axle casing alone for which a composite alternative is being considered is approximately 13 % of the entire rear axle assembly. There would be a potential 40 % approximate weight saving in the casing, by producing the casing only, from FRP instead of traditional steel. The benefit of the overall reduction in the axle mass is small when the complete axle assembly is considered. There are many design restrictions due to the driveline components; driving head and halfshafts, and the spindle ends. The geometry would have to remain similar to that of the current casing with the additional problem of heat dissipation from the driving head.

Another of the main design problems was the stiffness of the axle casing arm where the springseat and damper brackets would be mounted for the attachment of suspension components. It is envisaged that an uneconomical amount of FRP would be required to match the stiffness of the current steel casings. The flexural rigidity of the FRP would provide problems due to the containment of the drive axle within the axle arm. The drive axle is rigidly attached to the wheel and the driving head. The loading on the axle arm is a resultant of the horizontal and lateral forces exerted upon the wheel combined with the mass load of the vehicle. An FRP axle arm would be subjected to undesirable bending moment loadings. The driving gear is mounted inside the casing and has to be isolated from movement in order to maintain the spline alignment in the gears. Any displacement in the axle arm would result in detrimental damage to the driving components. However in the long term, if the manufacturing strategy of Albion Automotive is to develop a complete in-house manufacturing facility for solid rear axle casings then FRP materials are a solution. This is due to the greater cost and facility requirements that a steel forging plant would have in comparison to that required for a high volume, low pressure and low tooling costs, composite component manufacturing plant.

Fig 1 : A typical rear axle

Thus after a detailed examination of the rear axle casing it was concluded from the study that the existing design gave little opportunity for the application of composites. This is due to the manufacturing difficulties and design restrictions that the casing faces. These collectively go against the philosophy of composite component engineering, principally in the areas of parts consolidation and the non suitability of merely replacing a metal component with a composite one of similar design. This can be viewed in the potential costs for the casing halves and machining / design costs for the metal. The design issues concerning the metal inserts and the requirement for additional adhesive bonding technology will still be addressed and should be valuable to future product development.

An Independent Suspension System

Since the increase in production costs when compared to the steel axle currently manufactured are not justified by the technical benefits offered by a composite rear axle casing an independent suspension system was considered. The development of an FRP independent suspension system will provide the technological understanding and the basis upon which a composite rear axle casing could become a realistic proposal.

The development of an independent suspension system would also allow a better understanding of the requirements for an in-house production facility. Many of the problems facing the production of a solid rear casing do not exist in the design of an independent suspension system. At the same time it would provide adequate challenges in the development of the necessary adhesive bonding technology, FEA requirements and manufacturing process technology. Also there is the potential for incorporating the suspension as an integral part of the suspension arms through the realisation of the potential of composite material's physical properties.

The design of the components would be aimed at parts consolidation in the suspension geometry and a two piece driving head housing. The concept of an independent rear suspension is in line with the current automotive industry trend of research and development into vehicle suspension systems.

The problem of rigidity facing the solid rear axle casing is solved if the requirement for a rigid case is removed by the use of independent suspension. The strength/flexural modulus of the FRP could become an advantage in the design of the structural elements. One of the biggest problems facing the design of an independent suspension system are the packaging problem in terms of stress bearing areas in relation to the suspension volume. In the earlier designs incorporating five links the upper links intruded into the baggage compartments. However with the use of the half shaft as one of the upper links this problem has been solved by allowing the reduction in the size of the suspension arms. Part of the design specification of the project will be to investigate the parts consolidation potential offered by designing with FRPs.

The most efficient route for designing an independent suspension system is to have an axle module manufactured so as to be adaptable to a wide variety of chassis designs and applications. To date designers have tended to think of independent suspension vehicles rather than independent suspension modules for use on such vehicles. If designed and manufactured on a modular basis for application in a variety of vehicles this would be a logical approach and one that Albion currently use in the design of their current axle range. Live axle suspension systems are close to their optimum in regard to ultimate development.

Independent suspensions for heavy vehicles provides a whole range of possibilities³. This could be in the use of active suspension systems that could be controlled to suit the terrain or vehicle.

The FRP properties will be utilised to produce components that will be mechanically superior in terms of performance and cost effectiveness to current independent suspension system design using traditional materials. There will be less tooling requirements and less material requirements than those of the currently proposed FRP rigid axle casing. The requirement for reinforcement fibres around driving head casing will be less than that of the suspension linkage due to the reduction of structural forces seen by the driving head casing. Through the use of an appropriate resin system, the thermal conductivity and distortion problems of the application of composites in such an environment will be successfully tackled. Such a resin system is the DSM Daron hybrid resin system. The DSM hybrid resins allow for short processing times without the compromise on structural properties such as heat distortion, stiffness and strength.

Manufacturing Considerations

The advent of new RTM process changes have seen RTM move from a commercial, low performance process, to one that can be utilised for the fabrication of primary structural composite parts [4]. Therefore it is seen as a viable manufacturing process for consideration in this project. The RTM moulding process is very dependent on the properties of the polymers, fillers, reinforcements, moulds, and mechanical equipment. These are the key areas that the project is addressing concurrently with the component design. RTM composites can meet or surpass the properties exhibited by other fabrication methods, including autoclaved prepreg parts. Labour and part variability can be reduced while productivity can be increased. RTM provides the advantages of lower volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions with a closed mould process in terms of product uniformity (glass loading, thickness and physical properties) combined with relatively low investment costs.

These factors are all important to the success of implementing an FRP component manufacturing facility in the company. This is due to RTM being a low pressure process unlike many traditional composite manufacturing cold mould processes (sheet moulding compounds (SMCs) and reaction moulding compound (RIM). The compression moulding and injection moulding processes are well established but have considerable processing costs in terms of tooling and energy / high pressure requirements. The processes of RTM and reinforced reaction injection moulding (RRIM) in comparison offer the same capabilities but with much reduced plant costs. RTM is considered to offer the greatest potential for low volume production of complex components. RRIM is being considered also.

The design of the suspension componentry aims to allow the manufacturing process to involve heated flat sheets of FRP stamped into a three dimensional preform shell and subsequently installed over a moulded foam core. After the addition of some small, high performance attachment point preforms at certain high stress areas, the assembled preform is transferred to a heated steel tool for resin injection.

MARKET ANALYSIS

As equally important to the development of the design and manufacturing for the component are the market and financial considerations of using an FRP material in a market dominated by traditional materials and manufacturing methods. The consideration of these aspects on a concurrent basis with design and manufacture are not necessarily new to the company. However the project provides a forum for the successful combination of all of these aspects.

In the truck industry today, there is, and has been in the past, a limited application of composites and plastic materials. This can be partly explained by the overall truck industry's lack of acceptance of new material technology in structural applications. There has been widespread use of composites and plastic materials in tertiary applications in the cabs of trucks, especially of FRP. There are many components used in structural applications on trucks that have only been modified slightly in design over a period of decades in order to meet perhaps a heavier application. In cars Ford [5], Mercedes [6] and Rover [7] are examples of automotive manufacturers who have applied FRPs to structural applications in development work. The market acceptance of new components, conceptually different from the current products, is a big concern. This needs to be developed in order to estimate the sales-volume, selling-price/sales-revenue for an expected time period which would involve producing a business plan. Albion Automotive through the development of these new products hopes to enter new markets with possibly new product ranges.

Financial Implications

The use of composites is on an exponential increase with their application being applied across a wide field of technology. Fibre-reinforced composites, play an essential role in the aerospace industry where their properties have earned huge savings by reducing mass and providing the possibility for better aerodynamics, leading to huge fuel savings (one of the biggest costs in the industry). From the very early days of considering whether to use a new material or not, it is necessary to consider the financial aspects. Usually, there has to be an understanding first of the technical aspects of a new material. However, as soon as an assessment of the potential technical and performance benefits has been gained, it is then necessary to commence an assessment of the financial implications of the use of such a new material.

Commonly it is found that the initial use of the new material appears to increase the cost of production rather than decrease it. A new material may be in small-scale production compared with bulk production for previously-used materials and consequently costs much more per unit weight or volume. There is a requirement for the forward projections of output quantities and raw material volume-needs, in order to see how the price of the incoming raw material would fall with increased production. Also, a re-assessment of the design of the proposed new product is necessary to determine the benefits of the new material. These can be used to further reduce the number of components in the product giving parts consolidation leading to more efficient manufacturing procedures. From this procedure, other design benefits which can further give an overall reduction in production costs may arise.

The costs of new skills needed to carry through the R & D exercise and later manufacturing implementation needs to be taken into account early. This will include the increased cost of recruiting and training new skills in the areas of research work, design work and engineering

work. The later stages may involve the need for recruitment and training of manufacturing staff with better qualifications.

Tooling costs would be substantial area of concern when a new material/product is to be implemented. Composites can provide a reduction in tooling costs. For example, if RRIM materials are used instead of straight thermoplastic materials it is possible to not only reduce the cost of a moulding machine from potentially several hundred thousand pounds to several tens of thousands of pounds but the tooling costs drop from an average of many tens of thousands of pounds to merely some thousands of pounds [8].

At the initial stages in the product evaluation a market research assessment is necessary to determine the potential for the product. This will assess the customers' understanding of the product which the company is trying to sell them. The customer may have had no previous dealings with composite components and therefore be unaware of its potential when compared to traditional materials such as steel and aluminium.

The on-going costs which a manufacturer will have to consider include the increased cost of the up-keep of the new skills in research, design, engineering etc., which have been recruited. The comparison in the form of a cost benefit analysis will consider the new plant requirements, installation and maintenance. This would initially identify whether the new plant would be more profitable than the old plant (this would not be strictly applicable if the new plant was for the manufacture of a new product and was not for replacing existing machinery). The material costs are probably one of the initial hurdles to overcome in that composites are generally more expensive than the traditional metals but as production volumes increase this will decrease. The cost of new test procedures and test facilities must be taken into account. Often there is a higher cost initially with new materials than with the older materials since frequency of testing is usually higher in the early years. If the new material has been chosen wisely this cost usually declines to less than previous costs when adequate experience has been gained. From the above considerations the immediate and recurring costs can be estimated and combined to give an overall estimate of the costs of replacing the existing material/component with the composite material/component.

CONCLUSIONS

The TCS project outlined is providing Albion Automotive with an excellent opportunity to become an industry leader in the development of FRP automotive structural components. The research and development stages integrate material suppliers, educational establishments and the customers. A high profile approach backed with sound marketing can help the company create and sell such a product. The customers will have to be made aware of the benefits of such a product with any uncertainties in its ability to withstand the working conditions. A single marketing strategy is not suitable for application to the marketing of a new component manufactured from composites due to the current lack of market presence of composite components in the truck industry especially in the primary structural side of the market. Composites require an integrated design approach. Drucker [9] indicated that there are two distinct types of manufacturing industry: material based and information/knowledge based. This highlights that today the major driving force in the world economy is not the availability of materials but the availability of technology based innovation.

In the manufacture of composites components it is possible to target niche markets with economical short production runs. This is due to the design flexibility offered by composites which is necessary for the “fast to market” requirements of a flexible multi-vehicle chassis component manufacturer. The economic advantages are the reduction in costs associated with machining hours, assembly time, automated processes and lower cost modular tooling that could be adapted to suit a range of components.

In the company’s future strategic development involving FRP materials the TCS project between Albion Automotive and the University of Strathclyde is an excellent example of the two way transfer of technology from the university to industry. The adoption of a fresh approach to the design of existing components for application in composite materials using suitable composite design guidelines will ensure the success of the project for all parties involved. The project illustrates a successful product development process designed to give the desired performance for the optimum use of material with the manufacturing process concurrently developed alongside.

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